

Dora - Between a Freudian Oedipal Perspective and a Broader View

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Abstract

In this paper, I will address Freud's discovery of the power of interpretation in the healing of hysteria and neurosis in general. Dora (Ida Bauer) comes to Freud for treatment. I will describe Dora's path before treatment and the brief analysis she underwent with him. I will try to understand the hopes, longings, and desires that brought both Dora and Freud to analysis. I will review the pre-Oedipal perspective that has been written about the case and even try to deepen it.

Keywords: Suicide • Dora • Psych soma • Freud • Symptoms

Case Study

Dora in analysis

Philipp Bauer, a wealthy businessman, comes to Freud and requests treatment for his daughter, Dora. This request comes after a suicide letter that Dora wrote at the age of 18, which was found on her desk. About six years earlier, Philipp himself was in Freud's treatment for very severe symptoms—partly physiological and partly psychological—that left him helpless. Freud, in an intuitive flash, prescribes him treatment for syphilis, a disease he contracted before his marriage. Philipp's condition improves miraculously [1].

In the current meeting, Philipp tells Freud that he believes his daughter's current condition is related to the close relationship that has developed between his family and the K. family, who live near them. He further describes a deep emotional connection that developed between him and Mrs. K., who helped him greatly during his illness, and he has no desire to give up this connection. Philipp adds that deep relationships have developed between his daughter and Mr. K. Dora used to take care of the K. couple's children and thus became very friendly with Mr. K. Philipp reports that Dora's mental state has deteriorated greatly since they both spent a joint summer vacation with the K. family. During this vacation, Dora surprisingly demanded that he return home. She told her mother that Mr. K. tried to kiss her and offered her his love. Dora's father confronts Mr. K. with this information, and Mr. K. denies it completely. Since that event, the father says, Dora has been suffering from severe mood swings, isolating herself, and even demanding that he sever all ties with the K. couple. The father begs Freud to try to guide his daughter in better directions because his relationship with Mrs. K. is very dear to his heart [1].

Freud greatly appreciates Philipp and even calls him gifted. He writes that he never met Dora's mother. However, he adds that she is an uneducated woman who is not emotionally available to her children, with compulsive tendencies related to cleaning the house. She drives the household crazy with her cleaning impulses. Dora has an older brother with whom she had a close relationship, but recently they have grown very distant from each other [1].

Freud believes that Dora's love for her father has been greatly intensified over the years due to his many ailments. When she was six years old, he fell ill with tuberculosis. Due to his illness, the management of the business

was transferred to his brother, and Philipp and his family moved to a health resort. Dora says she felt social loneliness throughout this period. Dora started wetting the bed at night, a phenomenon that lasted about a year. Despite her young age, Dora devotes herself to caring for her father. She serves as a kind of sister to him and even becomes his confidante at times [2]. After Philipp recovers from his illness, he goes on a long visit to his factories, and Dora is forced into separation when she turns eight. In his absence, Dora suffers from significant shortness of breath. The medical instructions she receives are for plenty of rest, and Dora turns from a mischievous and energetic girl into a quiet and restrained one.

During this period, there was a great rapprochement between Dora and the K. family. Simultaneously with the outbreak of the disease. When Dora turned ten, her father began to lose sight in one eye, his healthy eye, as he had congenital blindness in his other eye. Again, Dora devotes herself to caring for him, and in an inexplicable way, the father suddenly begins to see with his congenitally blind eye. After another two years, the father suffers from meningitis, which causes him both physical and mental disabilities [2].

Simultaneous to the outbreak of the disease, there is a significant and noticeable rapprochement between Philipp and Mrs. K. Mrs. K. becomes his caregiver, while his wife, Dora's mother, becomes increasingly distant from him. When Mrs. K. enters the picture, Dora is stripped of her duties as her father's caregiver, and she begins to suffer from migraines and coughing fits, which turn into hoarseness until she loses her voice.

Due to the deterioration of Philipp's medical condition, Mr. K. recommends that Philipp turn to Freud, who, as mentioned, helped him greatly in the past. Philipp and Mrs. K.'s relationship grows stronger until it becomes a romantic relationship. At this stage, Dora is still unaware of the nature of her father's relationship with Mrs. K., and her relationship with Mr. K. also grows stronger. This is alongside the warming of her relationship with Mrs. K.

Dora is also close to the K. family's children. She sometimes takes care of them. At the same time, Mr. K. began buying her gifts and even sending her flowers every day [2].

The migraines from which Dora suffered passed, but the coughing fits remained throughout the years. The cough would develop into hoarseness until the loss of voice for weeks. Dora's symptoms were treated in the spirit of time, with painful water and electrical treatments that bore no fruit. Dora developed an antagonism to doctors in general and to her treatments in particular. In one of her coughing fits, her father suggested that she consult a doctor who had helped him greatly in the past; the doctor was Freud. Despite her reservations, Dora agreed. Freud recommended analysis, but Dora refused.

When Dora turned 16, she traveled with her family to visit the K. family during their vacation in a resort town. It was agreed that her father would only come for a few days, and then Dora would stay in the town for a few more weeks. Surprisingly, when the father was about to leave, Dora insisted on leaving with him. It was then that she claimed that Mr. K. had tried to kiss her

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by the lake and even offered her his love.

Since Dora's return from vacation, she has been depressed, exhausted, and avoided all social gatherings. She was very angry with her father and demanded that he sever his ties with the K. family.

At that time, her beloved aunt falls ill. Dora travels to her for an extended period. Dora suffers from severe abdominal pains, which were discovered to be an appendicitis attack. The aunt passed away, and Dora stays with her husband and daughters for another period of time. Around this time, Dora places the suicide letter on her desk. Dora's father is deeply shocked by the letter. About two days later, Dora lost consciousness after a bitter argument with her father about the K. family, and at the end of the event, Dora remembered nothing [1]. At this point in time, Philipp decided that Dora must meet Freud. Philipp reports to Freud what is happening with Dora, and Freud assumes that it is a simple story of a minor hysteria 'Petit hysterie' [2].

It is worth remembering that in those years, around 1900, many women were diagnosed with hysteria. A disease that aroused much helplessness in the medical community: a dismissive and blunt attitude, and even violence towards the patients. In this sense, Freud was different from the accepted approaches of his time. He was interested in the sick patients. He asked about every detail of their world and lives, and he guessed that he could help them by bringing to awareness fantasies and unconscious impulses that were their lot [2]. At that time, Freud begins to lose his confidence and skills and worries constantly due to his insufficient income [2]. When Dora arrives, he sees the treatment as an opportunity to prove how the interpretation of dreams can help to heal neurosis, as well as to establish his ideas, which he began to develop, regarding childhood sexuality and bisexuality [2].

Dora attends analysis six times per week. Freud does not direct her to speak specifically about her symptoms but allows her to speak freely. According to him, even if therapeutic material emerges in a fragmented manner, this style allows things to surface more accurately [1]. However, as he argued in his book *Studies on Hysteria* [3], he still maintains that at the root of every hysterical case lies an early trauma of a sexual nature. He writes, "...Dora told me about an earlier occurrence with Mr. K. that could have even more so caused a trauma of a sexual nature..." [1]. Dora recounts to Freud another event that occurred with Mr. K. when she was 13.5 years old. In this event, he pressed his body against her and began kissing her on the lips. She says she felt nauseous, ran home, and tried to distance herself from him. Despite this, their relationship continued without either of them mentioning what had happened. Freud notes that Mr. K. is a man with an attractive appearance, and he expected that an event of this kind would also arouse some degree of sexual stimulation in Dora. In his opinion, Dora's reaction of disgust was actually a hysterical reaction, in which there is a reversal of affects—from attraction to disgust — and there is also displacement — from stimulation of the genitals to stimulation of the digestive system in the form of nausea [1].

In her meetings with Freud, Dora rarely talks about Mr. K. and is mainly preoccupied with her anger towards her father. She reports in great detail about the formation of the relationship between her father and Mrs. K., alongside the disappearance of her mother. She describes how Mrs. K. transformed from a sickly woman into a healthy and vibrant woman because of these relationships. Her father repeatedly visits the K. family under various pretexts and even sends Dora and her mother cheerful and lively letters from there. Dora describes her father as a hypocrite who thinks only of himself and satisfying his needs. She adds angrily that she was, in effect, abandoned by him and given to Mr. K. as a consolation prize for his tolerance of the relationship between him and Mrs. K., his wife. Freud sees how the father ignored what was not convenient for him to see, but at the same time, Freud suspects that Dora's emphatic accusations against her father also contain hidden self-accusations with the same content. Freud believes that Dora, too, ignored things that happened right under her nose with Mr. K. Until that incident in the resort town, Dora chose to ignore all the signs that were extended to her, and in fact, almost assisted in her father's relationship with Mrs. K. (she used to take the children when her father came to visit Mrs. K.). Freud wondered if Dora had an interest in maintaining her father's relationship with Mrs. K. He is increasingly forming the idea that Dora's relationships with Mr. K.'s children were actually concealment from

herself and others that she is actually in love with Mr. K. himself. Freud presents this thought to her, and Dora says she does not remember feeling that way. However, she admits that her cousin says that she looks in love with Mr. K. Later, she even admits that until the incident at the lake, she fell in love with Mr. K. But since then, she does not feel that way. Freud concludes that Dora's desire to maintain her father's relationship with Mrs. K. stems from Dora's unconscious desire to ensure that Mr. K. is available and accessible for a relationship with her.

In one of the following sessions, Dora arrives with a stomachache. Freud estimates that it is an imitation of someone and asks about it. Dora says that she has returned from a visit to the daughters of her beloved aunt who died, and her cousin complained of severe abdominal pains, following which she was sent to a sanatorium in the mountains. Freud sees a sequence of illnesses alongside the benefits they bring:

Mrs. K. - becomes ill and reaps benefits from it.

Dora's father - becomes ill, is sent to the mountains, and coordinates this with Mrs. K.

Dora's mother - becomes ill whenever her husband returns from his travels and thus avoids any contact with him.

Freud assumes that a connection has been created in Dora between illness and love/closeness. This connection, in his understanding, helps to understand her symptoms. Freud believes that this pattern appeared already at the beginning of Dora's attacks but was blurred later in order to hide the connections from herself and others. When her beloved, Mr. K., was distant due to his travels, Dora gave up speaking (loss of voice) and, on the other hand, became a fluent and flowing writer, because she wrote many letters to him [1].

As is known, according to Freud's understanding, one of the explanations for the hysterical symptom will necessarily also be the realization of a sexual fantasy, and even a perverse fantasy. When Dora claims to Freud that Mrs. K. is in love with her father only because of his means (money), Freud makes a reversal and concludes that her father actually has no "means" in the sexual context. That is, he lacks virility. Dora confirms this. Freud concludes that she is referring to oral sexual stimulation, and even connects these statements to her coughing fits, which symbolize her identification with Mrs. K. These explanations of Freud are received by Dora in silence, and her cough disappears [1].

Freud believes that Dora reacts to her father's affairs as if she were his partner (it's either her or me) and on the other hand, in identification with Mrs. K. (the cough as oral sexual stimulation). Freud further concludes that Dora's love for her father is greater than she herself knows and that she is actually in love with him. He believes that Dora's childhood infatuation with her father is now revived in order to hide, even from herself, her infatuation with Mr. K. He presents this interpretation to Dora, and she objects. This objection is understood by Freud as repression. And the strength of the "no" as the strength of the repression [1].

In one of the meetings, Dora tells Freud about a dream that she dreamed three nights in a row after the incident with Mr. K. at the lake. Freud asks her to bring up associations to this dream. Dora tells of a quarrel between her parents because her mother locks the kitchen door every night, thereby preventing her brother from leaving his room in case something happens at night. Another association that comes up in Dora is that lightning will strike their wooden cabin in the resort town. In addition, she says that she asked to lock her room in the resort cabin for fear that Mr. K. would enter while she was dressing, but she could not find a key. She remembers that Mr. K. gave her an expensive jewelry box as a gift. From her reactions, Freud concludes that this is material that has undergone massive repression. In German, the meaning of "jewelry box" is also the female genitalia. Freud tells Dora that she was actually afraid that Mr. K. would enter her room and take her "jewelry box" from her. In addition, he says that she felt that it would be her father's fault, so she dreamed everything in reverse. Instead of her father being guilty, he is the one who comes in the dream to save her. Dora further remembers a beautiful and expensive piece of jewelry that her father bought for her mother, and she did not like it. Freud

interprets this as Dora's desire to give her father what her mother is unwilling to give him. By analogy, she is willing to give Mr. K. what Mrs. K. prevents him from having.

Freud interprets Dora's dream as a decision to withdraw from the lake, where there is a danger to her virginity. He sees this as Dora's attempt to suppress the temptation to submit to a man. Freud assumes that in the dream, she flees with the father, but in reality, she escapes to her father. Freud concludes that more than Dora's fear of Mr. K, she fears that she will not overcome the temptation to surrender to him. Dora opposes Freud's interpretations [1].

A few weeks after the first dream, Dora presents another dream. Without delving into the details of the dream, it is noted that Freud assumes it reflects a fantasy concerning the loss of virginity, and he likens the appendicitis that occurs nine months later to childbirth. Freud believes that Dora continues to love Mr. K internally, and by preserving her symptoms, she continues to unconsciously experience her love for him [1]. After Freud completes the interpretation of the dream, Dora informs him that she will cease attending analysis in two weeks. Freud responds by stating that her announcement reminds him of a resignation notice for a nanny or servant. Consequently, Dora recalls that Mr. K's children's nanny had told her a similar story regarding Mr. K's courtship of her. This fact further humiliates Dora, as Mr. K treats her as a nanny or servant.

Freud shares with Dora his thoughts on her desire for Mr. K to divorce Mrs. K and marry her. In his view, their relationship is supported by the idea that Mrs. K would wish to divorce, thereby making Mr. K available to marry her. Dora does not express any opposition, bids farewell to Freud very kindly and does not return to treatment [1].

Freud wonders whether Dora's sudden departure could have been avoided had he placed more emphasis on the importance of her remaining in treatment or if he had provided her with warmer attention—an attention that would serve as a substitute for the love that Dora so longed for. He adds that despite his appreciation for theory, he maintains the position that psychological influence necessarily has its limits, and he respects the wishes and insights of each patient [1].

Freud acknowledges that the treatment of Dora was brief and insufficient. He believes that Dora's homosexual attraction to Mrs. K is her most significant unconscious component and regrets not having brought this to her attention.

Several years after the completion of Dora's analysis, Freud presents the concept of transference for the first time. "A whole series of early mental experiences is not felt as a relic of the past but comes to life as a current reference to the figure of the therapist [1]. "Transference, which is meant to be the central obstacle in analysis, becomes the most powerful tool for it if one can recognize it each time and translate it for the patient. Freud concludes that the treatment of Dora and its premature end can be understood only through the comprehension of the transference that occurred within it. He explains that the part of her that reminded her of Mr. K provokes in her the impulse for revenge against him; thus, she abandons him as she believes she was abandoned by Mr. K [1].

Why did the analysis end prematurely?

A significant amount has been written about the treatment of Dora. Most authors, while acknowledging Freud's genius, have criticized his therapeutic approach. Broadly, I will categorize the critiques into three categories:

First category

Freud the Theoretician Freud was so determined to establish his theory during this period and to demonstrate the importance of interpretation in the healing of symptoms that he distanced himself considerably from Dora's own feelings [4,5]. From the beginning of the treatment, Freud was convinced he understood her internal dynamics, which were producing her symptoms and suffering. He became resolute in convincing her of the validity of his approach. This determination made it difficult for him to genuinely listen to her protests. Dora remained trapped in an impossible limbo: everything she said was

interpreted through his understanding, and any resistance was interpreted as repression [6].

Second category

Limitations of Freud's Psychoanalytic Understanding at the Time (Transference), at the time Freud treated Dora, he did not fully comprehend the power of transference processes and countertransference. His definition of transference was presented only in the "Afterword," several years after the end of Dora's treatment. This category also includes unresolved and unconscious conflicts within Freud himself, which enhanced the capacity for compassion and tenderness he could express towards Dora [2]. Deutsch F [6] highlights the similarities between Dora and Anna O., Breuer's patient. She posits that a chain of associations linked the two patients in Freud's mind, evoking an unconscious fear of the dangers associated with intense relationships with a young patient. As a reminder, Breuer's therapeutic relationship with Anna O. threatened to cause a crisis in his marriage, leading to the premature termination of her treatment. Dekker HS [2] also notes that the sexual distance that characterized Freud's relationship with his wife at that time heightened this fear. Freud S and Joseph B [3] suggests that Dora elicited unconscious associations in Freud related to the nanny who abandoned him in childhood. He speculates that this early drama in Freud's life awakened residues that manifested in his relationships with Dora. Finally, some hypothesize that the themes with incestuous overtones that Dora addressed threatened to bring to Freud's consciousness distressing content regarding his own identity. These conflictual issues, according to Freud's critics, complicated the treatment with negative emotional burdens that made it difficult for Freud to be more open and attentive to Dora.

Third category

In this critique, Spiegel R [7] discusses the connection between Freud's attitude towards sexuality, sexual trauma, and its treatment. Spiegel mentions the dramatic shift in Freud's perception of childhood sexuality. In his book "Studies on Hysteria" Freud regarded the sexual fantasies of his female patients as factual occurrences [3]; however, in the case of Dora, he made an excessive correction: Freud viewed actual events as fantasies and cast doubt on the real-life seductions that occurred. Thus, despite labeling the two incidents that Dora experienced with Mr. K as traumatic sexual events, he did not acknowledge to Dora the traumatic impact of these events on her. Not only did Freud fail to validate the difficulties inherent in Dora's experiences with Mr. K, but he also emphasized her attraction and desire for a sexual relationship with him. Additionally, Glen [8] highlights that due to Dora's young age, Freud's sexual interpretations may have been experienced by her as seductive and dangerous. Pre-Oedipal Understanding: When reading Dora's case description, the absence of a maternal figure in her life is striking. I hypothesize that the lack of a maternal figure obscures Dora's original wounds, which are so closely related to her deficient relationships with her mother. Therefore, I surmise that as much as Dora's connections revolve around her father, they also revolve around the psychological absence of her mother in her life. Already in the presentation of the anamnesis, the father is depicted in detail, and Freud believes he constitutes the most significant figure in Dora's life. In contrast, the mother is presented in a vague and brief manner: "I conceived an image of a woman with little education and, above all, not very wise (Freud, 1993, pp. 38-39) [1]." The details that Freud provides about Dora's mother, such as her tendency towards compulsive cleaning and her emotional absence, are supported by additional sources. Rogow AA [9] describes the mother's behavior in the household: "No one could enter the Bauer household without first removing their shoes... On days of thorough cleaning, everyone had to leave the house" [9]. Similarly, Felix Deutsch, who met Dora when she was 40, wrote: "She spoke mainly about her relationship with her mother, about her unhappy childhood due to her mother's excessive cleanliness demands, and the emotional absence she displayed toward her [9]." It seems to me that even if Freud did not intend this, one can retrospectively attribute symbolic meaning to the narrow place allotted to her mother in the narrative of Dora's life. This narrow space may represent the meager emotional presence of the mother in Dora's psychological life. A search I conducted for psychoanalytic literature addressing the missing maternal aspects in Dora's context yielded several sources. In 1973, Lewin KK [10] wrote that Freud identified Dora's attraction to

Mrs. K as critical to her understanding, thus approaching the psychological truth of Dora. However, Levin argues that Freud did not explore this aspect thoroughly. He believes that the attraction to Mrs. K did not stand alone but was actually a substitute or displacement for Dora's yearning for her mother's love. According to him, Dora's ultimate desire was for her mother's absolute and exclusive love, which was never given to her. In 1979, Possick S [11] wrote similarly. He describes Dora's mother as a cold, rejecting, insensitive, and inaccessible woman. He believes that the feelings of abandonment and rejection by her mother led Dora to simultaneously hate and identify with her. Pusik argues that Freud's sexual interpretations missed the childlike need of Dora that lay behind them. Moreover, Freud's positioning toward Dora, as if he were the "key" to her inner world, caused her to feel as though he had no genuine interest in her and ignored her needs in a way that replicated her abandonment by her mother, contributing to negative transference [11]. In 1993, Ornstein PH [12], from a Kohutian perspective, writes about Dora. He argues that the intensity, recurrence, and persistence of Dora's various ailments, as well as the "toxic" familial and environmental factors, indicate early and ongoing traumatization. The description of the mother and the relationship between the two raises the hypothesis of very inaccurate and even unreliable reflections. In the absence of a suitable response to her needs, Dora remained "hungry" and unfulfilled. Therefore, like Pusik, Ornstein argues that the perception of issues arising from an Oedipal source "missed" the much earlier roots that motivate Dora's difficulties. Like Levin, Ornstein sees the sexual attraction to Mrs. K as representing the intensity of longing and the desire to reunite with the missing maternal figure. The question now arises: How did this absence of the mother register in Dora's psyche? I believe that an answer to this can be found in Dora's first dream. In the dream, Dora and her family are in a survival-threatening situation due to a fire threatening to consume them. Dora's mother is not engaged in saving them; instead, she is preoccupied with her jewelry box. It seems she lacks a basic maternal instinct, investing her resources in something trivial at such a critical time. I propose that this dream, with its content and the associations it raises in Dora, represents early areas of the psyche, where the ego is in its most exposed, vulnerable, and survival-related experience. This experience is represented in the dream by the fire threatening to annihilate all the inhabitants of the house. If I continue in this direction, the mother is supposed to absorb the panic of survival, to blend in with it, to be frightened herself, to digest, and to return the Beta materials in a digested form [5]. Instead, she remains emotionally detached, remote, and uninvolved. Even through the associations Dora conveys to Freud regarding her dream, she conveys a record of a disconnected mother (with compulsive locking defenses), while the father compensates, thinks, and cares for them. (What will happen if something occurs at night, and the mother locks the kitchen and the son's escape route?) It appears that through this dream, Dora conveys to Freud a fundamental feeling that registered in her psyche: the absence of a present maternal figure, called to hear, know, and act! A somewhat anxious, somewhat depressed mother, a present yet absent figure a variation of the "dead mother" [13]. Against this backdrop, I understand Dora's intense search for a warm and close relationship with her father, with Mr. K, and with Mrs. K, precisely as a healthy part of Dora's psyche. This part knows that there should be an anchoring point of a warm, close, nurturing, and admiring relationship. A relationship that could serve as a substitute for the unsuccessful relationship with her mother and allow for the growth of a true self, a sense of worth, and meaning. Paradoxically, the closeness that Dora experienced while caring for her father's numerous ailments served as a corrective and meaningful experience for her. The very closeness to him, the sense of meaning he provided her with. Subsequently, when Mrs. K assumed her position as the caregiver for her father, migraines and severe coughing began to appear. The physical distance from her father once again manifests physically. However, it is still evident that Dora and Mrs. K enjoyed each other's company, and this relationship somewhat serves as a substitute for the missing connections with her mother. Around this time, Dora identifies Mr. K's affection for her. She enjoys his libidinal investment in her. Now, the symptom of shortness of breath that appears for the first time when her father travels after his recovery appears in a different way. Whenever Mr. K travels, she is seized with coughing and loss of voice. It seems that Mr. K's travels (his temporary absence) echo in Dora the original wound of her mother's psychological absence from her inner life. Furthermore, even if, as

Freud believed, Dora felt an Oedipal sexual attraction to Mr. K, I do not think Dora hoped that this fantasy would be realized. It seems to me that Mr. K's suggestions for fulfilling the relationship were traumatic for her, and it would have been appropriate for Freud to express this explicitly. This trauma seems to resonate even more deeply with the original wound, which manifested in Dora's recurring dream after the incident at the lake. In fact, Dora felt betrayed by all the figures she so longed for their love: Mr. K, who violated all the taboo rules and denied guilt; Mrs. K, who took her father from her; and her father, who, in her feeling, was willing to turn a blind eye to the prolonged harm done to her in order to maintain his ties with Mrs. K. Now, Dora dares to expose herself to Freud and experiences similar feelings from him, who returns the blame to her. Marcus S [14] helps us understand that Dora, as a teenager between the ages of 13 and 18, experienced severe despair. The three adults she loved more than anyone else conspired against her—individually, one after the other, and together—to rob her of the reality of her experiences. They effectively denied Dora her reality, and even the reality itself! Such betrayal can easily destabilize the psyche of a young person: for not only did they betray Dora's love and belief, but also the structure of the real world. One must also consider that these dramas, occurring in her life during adolescence, rest on a shaky foundation with her mother, built on wounded and disturbed grounds. In light of all this, Dora transforms from a mature child, a partner in deep conversations, into a whiny, complaining, isolated, angry, and sad teenager. All of these also indicate the traumatic nature of the event she experienced with Mr. K. Therefore, unlike Freud, who viewed Dora's suicide note as a manipulative act, I see it as a genuine and profound cry of distress. It seems to me that through the letter, Dora attempts to convey distress and pain over the loss of meaning and value in her life, as her entire world collapses, and she has no one left to rely on. The sequence of losses of significant figures in her life ignited the early, wounded areas of her psyche, stemming from the early trauma of the absence of the mother-child connection. A trauma that, in Winnicott's words [15], "occurred but was not experienced." This perspective I propose does not negate Freud's viewpoint about Dora and her dreams. It is reasonable to assume that there is also a sexual interpretation of the jewelry box, the dense forest, the nymphs, and more. However, it seems to me that Freud and Dora were not yet ready to engage with these contents and acknowledge them in therapy. It appears that both Freud and Dora needed to undergo a few more stages along the way. Had Freud validated and affirmed Dora's feelings regarding her father, Mr. K, and Mrs. K, Dora would have felt more understood, held, and contained. The therapeutic alliance could thus begin to take shape. Furthermore, by allowing space for her emotional absence of her mother and the implications that this absence carved in her psyche, Freud could have greatly assisted Dora in connecting with the fundamental truth of her life (this stage may have involved regression to dependency). Such contact could have helped Dora understand herself coherently, give meaning to her feelings, and connect her more deeply and authentically with herself. The difficulties with her father and with the K couple could then have been understood as de-traumatization, which would have lent greater validity to her powerful feelings. It seems to me that only when these processes were well established could there be room for processing the Oedipal sexual processes proposed by Freud.

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